

MICRODESIGN OF LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the present work involved configuring a personal computer based design aid for use by engineering students when determining in-plane stresses and strains of composite laminate materials. Most fibre composite design computer programs require extensive input of laminate properties which are attained in most cases by physical testing, and from the individual laminate properties; the fibre properties are back calculated. Micro-mechanical design involves treating the laminate as a number of plies. Calculations are then performed for each ply group to find its fundamental engineering mechanical property. The laminate properties are found based on the state of the ply properties. Back calculation involves using known laminate properties (E_{f_x} , E_{f_y} , $E_{f_{xy}}$, etc) from using micromechanical theory. The basis of the present work is that of forward calculation which employs fibre and matrix properties to determine laminate properties. Details are given of numerical input and output together with graphical results. These indicate that a spreadsheet approach together with forward calculation for composite laminate design provides an approach to initial design calculations.

KEYWORDS: Design Methodology, Micromechanics, Laminate, Strength, Volume fraction

1. INTRODUCTION

The back calculation approach is most commonly used for composite laminate design. This approach requires the least amount of calculated or material and service data and is often iterative in arriving at design guidelines (1). However, it is often of interest to determine these guidelines according to a Forward Calculation approach, i.e. various laminate and fibre/matrix properties are derived and employed as an input for final calculations, so against an iterative process is followed.

This approach is useful if fibre and matrix properties are well known and established. The process described below is an attempt at such a design step for use by engineering students in a materials design course. Utilising elementary composite constituent properties a laminate configuration is established employing a microcomputer spreadsheet language package. A comparison with back calculation design guidelines is shown.

2. BASIC APPROACH

2.1 Computer Equipment The majority of computer packages able to be utilised for laminate design are those which are based on finite element programs (FE) and which were originally developed for the aerospace, automotive and shipbuilding industry (2-5) However, their use requires both highly trained personnel, and often main-frame and or mini computers. For those users who do not have either or both access to large computers and sophisticated programming and analysis capabilities, they are often able to use microcomputers.(6-9). These items of analysis and calculation are now to be found in almost every engineering design office as well as the laboratory; they are not as draining on the budget or brain power. For the present work the principles of spreadsheet analysis are employed for programming, analysis of results and graphical display..

2.2 Composite Representation The definition of a composite is complex because of the orthotropic nature of laminate. A composite material is simply defined, for the purpose of this program, as a fibre-reinforced material containing a number of plies. Each ply has unidirectional fibres in a resin matrix. However, the fibres in each ply may be orientated at an angle to fibres in other or adjoining plies. There is no practical limit to the number of laminates, with the only restriction

being the size of the hard disk on the micro-computer This simplification aids the student in understanding basic design concepts.

2.3 Back Calculation vis a vis Forward Calculation An important aspect to grasp about this program is that it Forward calculates rather than Back calculates. The terms Forward calculations and Back calculations are defined as follows:

Forward calculation is the process by which mechanical and physical laminate properties, are determined by using existing micromechanical formulae from properties of the fibre and matrix materials.

Back calculation is the process by which a laminate is physically tested for actual laminate/ply fundamental properties (e.g. Young's modulus and tensile strength). Because the matrix properties are known, these same micromechanical formulas can be utilised to determine the fibre properties.

3. LAMINATE ANALYSIS

3.1 Micromechanics of Laminates

The micro-mechanics option of creating laminates in the computer spreadsheet program was specifically written to allow the user the capability of modelling laminates, without having to know the layer properties beforehand. Whereas, the macro-mechanics option is used typically for modelling prepared laminates, with the layer properties being known.

Lamination theory is used as a tool to model all types of laminates. A description of this theory is not given here and a greater explanation can be found, in for example, many sources(10,11).

The micromechanics approach proposes that the interaction of the constituent materials are able to be analysed on a microscopic scale. Generally, basic formulation describing elastic behaviour of composites are based upon this approach. Alternatively, this approach analyses the behaviour of fibre-reinforced composite material subjected to mechanical loads, when considered as a whole structure. The material is assumed to be homogeneous for all calculation.

For the microcomputer program a laminate is constructed by arranging a number of plies in a stacking sequence. The laminates are defined from individual fibre and resin matrix properties. Laminate types range through unidirectional, angle-ply, and cross-ply.

4. MICRODES

4.1 Introduction In this section we illustrate the principles of the spreadsheet based composite laminate analysis program which we named MICRODES. It was designed to assist students with little expertise in programming languages and who have access to a micro-computer and a spreadsheet program. Through their studies in engineering design, novice engineers often require decisions of an interactive and "what-if" nature. For most practical purposes the spreadsheet technique allows 'open' programming, i.e. all input, calculations, and results are visible on the screen and many parameters may be altered.

4.2 Design with Failure For design purposes, the program provides output indicating two forms of expected failure (FPF or LPF), allowing a quick assessment for composite selection. The designer has then at his/her fingertips a useful tool for an approximate quick calculation as a first step to a more serious integrated design. Once those steps have been achieved a complete FE analysis, for example, may be performed. However, there is no guarantee that the results will be more accurate than the "spreadsheet" approach.

Aside from generating various laminate properties, the program determines the failure condition for the laminate. It does this by using Tsai-Wu quadratic failure criteria (10,11) to find the strength ratio R for each ply. The strength ratio is defined in general terms as: allowable strength divided by the actual strength. The strength ratio provides a means of determining the additional load capacity of each layer of a laminate under a specific loading condition. In some respects, the strength ratio is similar to a safety factor, but with composite materials, the failure mechanisms are usually complex and predicting ultimate strengths of a laminate is difficult. Predicted failure of a layer does not necessarily constitute laminate failure. The MICRODES program utilises this failure criteria technique to estimate the strengths of the layers, but also allows the user to modify these estimates.

An upper and lower bound approach is employed to determine laminate failure. First-ply-failure (FPF) implies that a laminate composite can only be useful in design until the first ply fails. Consequently, a lower

bound minimum can be utilised for design. On the other hand, an ultimate or last-ply-failure (LPF) approach intimates that the laminate is useful for supporting loads until there is failure of the last ply and so is an upper bound approach for actual design purposes. A safety factor is applied to either LPF or FPF and the actual condition used to design is independent in the environment in which the composite laminates will be utilised.

Microdes, similar to another spreadsheet package (12) for composite materials) laminate analysis, provides immediate results for a wide variety of design situation. This is particularly useful for students involved in design projects. It takes into account the nature of the matrix and fibres, or a complete laminate, the loading case, and the necessity of some safety factor. To simplify the use for students, a menu-approach guides user to the procedure for a total analysis. The user can either access a data base of material properties or input specific information. Comparison of two major constituent, fibre volume fraction for one resin/fibre system, or of different composite constituents for a particular fibre volume fraction may be assessed.

Similar to other programs (12-15), graphical comparisons of fibre volume fractions are able to be made to simplify the selection process and design criteria. The analysis system is designed such that the user is guided in a hierarchical manner to supply the necessary data or indicate where such data exists on computer files. Forward calculation is utilised for obtaining laminate data. Assuming that back calculations are also accurate and reliable, a comparison of the two approaches can then be made by students in a design class.

5. OUTLINE OF ANALYSIS PROCEDURES

The overall approach to simple composite laminate design is discussed below.

5.1 Example of MICRODES Spreadsheet Approach Utilising a spreadsheet approach data input is simplified, iterative process may be quickly carried out, and small changes of conditions may be implemented without a complete analysis. Following from this concept but with a forward calculation process the preliminary design process may be speeded up compared with a conventional programming approach. A flow chart of the design process highlighting all procedures is shown in Figure 1.

compared with a conventional programming approach. A flow chart of the design process highlighting all procedures is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Outline of analysis hierarchy

As an example of the input, calculations, and output from the MICRODES program consider the following situation: a parallel laminate of PAN-carbon [T300] is made up in an epoxy matrix.

The configuration of the laminates is as follows: $[0_5/45_2/60_2/90_5]_S$: the in-plane forces are $N_{xx} = 500 \text{ N.mm}^{-1}$; $N_{yy} = 250 \text{ N.mm}^{-1}$; $N_{xy} = 125 \text{ N.mm}^{-1}$ per unit thickness. Operating temperature of $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Samples of a selection of pages of the program shown on the computer screen are shown in Figures 2,3 and 4 where:

Figure 2 - frontispiece instructions for input, analysis and output

Figure 3 - numerical input of ply data and loads

To aid in design situations, resultants are given in terms of R values since they are non-dimensional and may be considered as a form of safety factor if greater than unity(10). These calculations from MICRODES give results for the laminas under the two failure conditions of FPF and LPF. Figure 4 shows a comparison between the R-ratios for FPF and LPF when

when applied to for example allowable stress. Further they allow an assessment of either the form of failure criteria required and the amount of fibre to achieve the appropriate strength level. However, these results need to be assessed, so the student designer performs similar calculations with a back calculation spreadsheet program (12)

A comparison of the results obtained from these two approaches for one volume fraction but a number of ply orientations is given in Table 1 for T300/Epoxy composite described above.

COMPOSITE	CALCULATION TYPE		PLY GROUP ORIENTATION (angle)			
			0	45	60	90
T300	FPF	forward	1.35	1.27	1.16	0.97
		back	1.34	1.06	1.01	0.95
		% difference	0.75	19.8	18.4	2.1
T300	LPF	forward	1.59	1.94	2.29	2.77
		back	1.52	1.76	1.93	2.06
		% difference	4.6	10.2	15.4	33.1

Table 1: Comparison of R-values utilising back and forward approaches.

The results given in Table 1 indicate that there is general overall agreement of up to 2% for either 0/90 and within 20% for 45/60 for FPF which is quite acceptable considering that input data is often very variable. However there is agreement only within 20% for 0/45/60 degrees plies (similar to FPF) however for LPF the discrepancies are larger. These are currently being investigated by one of my graduate students and the results are not presently available.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The analysis procedure uses the properties from the data files to Forward calculate the strength properties of a unidirectional laminate. It then performs additional calculations to determine design properties of the laminate in terms of the R ratio for loading conditions.

The composite laminate software may be used as a general aid for design by engineering students and designers alike.

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IN-PLANE FIBRE COMPOSITE DESIGN AID

This is the main menu screen for the spreadsheet . To run the particular menu applications listed below , simply press Alt+letter .

Macro Designation	Application
Alt A	Brings you back to menu screen (this screen)
Alt B	Input laminate configuration and In-plane forces
Alt C	Choose a fibre material or laminate
Alt D	Choose a matrix material for laminate
Alt E	Display unidirectional lamina properties
Alt F	Display stresses & strains in laminate
Alt G	Display stresses in principle dir. of plys
Alt H	Display R values for FPF & LPF,also σ_0 & σ_{ult}
Alt I	Change stress partitioning factors
Alt J	Change degradation factor
Alt K	Examine effect of changing volume fraction of fibre
Alt L	Compares three laminates w.r.t change of vol. frac.
ALT M	Choose a general laminate to work with

N.B Once all input is completed , press F9 for recalculation .

FIGURE 2: FRONTISPIECE INSTRUCTIONS FOR INPUT ANALYSIS AND OUTPUT

INPUT OF LAMINATE OR PLY CONFIGURATION AND IN-PLANE FORCES

Move the cursor to the variable you want changed , enter the new variable and press return . Press Alt A to return to main menu .

	THETA(angle)				
	THETA 1	THETA 2	THETA 3	THETA 4	REPEAT
Orietation of ply group	0	45	60	90	1
Number of plys in group	5	2	2	5	
.....					
OPERATING TEMPERATURE (degrees C)	25				
.....					
IN-PLANE FORCES (N/mm)					
Force in x-direction :-	Nxx	500			
Force in y-direction :-	Nyy	250			
Force in shear (xy) :-	Nxy	125			
.....					

FIGURE 3: NUMERICAL INPUT OF PLY DATA

Figure 4: Calculated R Ratios for FPF and LPF in relation to fibre volume fraction

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